

Multidisciplinary Optimisation of High Pressure Turbine Blade Tip With Turbine Inlet Capacity and Stage Reaction Constraints

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This work deals with aerodynamic and aerothermal optimisations of high pressure turbine blade tips where a winglet turbine tip is optimised in terms of both aerodynamic efficiency and integrated heat transfer coefficient. Two constraints were introduced in the optimisation process. In particular, turbine mass flow, defined as a non-dimensional turbine inlet capacity, and stage reaction were constrained to change for up to $\pm 0.5\%$ from the datum values. Turbine inlet capacity and stage reaction constraints were achieved by skewing the rotor blade of turbine stage. Steady RANS simulations with $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model were performed for the turbine stage using multi-block fully structured mesh and a mixing plane between the stator and the rotor domain. Gradient based optimiser was used in all the optimisations performed. Aerodynamic optimisation was performed first, with and without the constraints, followed by multidisciplinary optimisation done in three steps. By varying the objective weights to explore the Pareto front, winglet designs with considerable efficiency improvements for only minor increase in heat load were identified, featuring sharp leading edge and suction side overhangs. On the other hand, sharp edges were found to be prone to local aerodynamic heating, highlighting the importance of the aerothermal assessment of this problem.

I. Nomenclature

HPT	=	high pressure turbine
HTC	=	heat transfer coefficient
OTL	=	over tip leakage
PS	=	pressure side
SS	=	suction side
LE	=	leading edge
TE	=	trailing edge
PV	=	passage vortex
A	=	area
C	=	chord
T	=	temperature
Nu	=	Nusselt number
h	=	enthalpy
k	=	thermal conductivity
\dot{m}	=	mass flow
p	=	pressure
q	=	wall heat flux
η	=	turbine efficiency
Φ	=	turbine capacity
Λ	=	turbine reaction

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II. Introduction

Over tip leakage flow is one of the main sources of loss in the high pressure turbines and, according to Denton [1], is responsible for up to one third of the total HPT stage loss. It is driven by the pressure difference between the pressure and the suction side of the rotor blade. The leakage of fluid, apart from the aerodynamic mixing losses, also influences the thermal performance of the blade, causing complex heat flux patterns on the blade tip with negative effects on both aerodynamic efficiency and durability of the turbine. To mitigate turbine tip leakage flow, there are two common approaches. The first is the use of shrouded blade tips, effective in preventing the leakage flow, but depending on the upstream combustion temperature, may require more coolant flow. Also, shrouded blade tips increase weight and limit rotational speed due to the increased mechanical stress of the blade. Second tip leakage mitigation approach is the use of unshrouded blade tips which are usually divided into flat tip, winglet tip and squealer tip blades. Depending on the tip geometry, unshrouded tips mitigate the leakage flow by decreasing the pressure difference, by creating a sealing effect, or their combinations.

Review of shrouded and unshrouded blades and their aerothermal performance has been given by number of authors, e.g. Harvey [2] and Bunker [3, 4]. Over tip leakage flow in flat tip turbine rotors was explained by Coull and Atkins [5]. As the leakage flow enters the flat tip gap, it is separated at the pressure side edge, forming a separating bubble along the pressure side edge. This separation bubble and a boundary layer formed downstream of it, narrow the effective tip gap, decreasing the amount of leakage flow. If the blade is wide enough, leakage flow separated at PS edge will reattach on the tip surface forming a heat transfer hotspot. Because of the relative movement of the casing, boundary layer is formed on the casing side, further reducing the effective tip gap. All this can lead to supersonic conditions of leakage flow inside the tip gap that can form a series of oblique shocks. Those oblique shocks impinge on the tip surface causing stripes of increased heat transfer as shown by Zhang et al. [6, 7].

Key and Arts [8] compared flat tips and squealer tips and Vass and Arts [9] investigated different squealer designs with and without openings. Both partial and full perimeter squealers were found to operate like labyrinth seals where each squealer rim causes additional flow separation, blocking the leakage flow [10]. As the flow enters squealer tip gap, contracting over the PS rim, it forms a pressure side corner vortex inside the squealer cavity in the corner between PS rim and the cavity floor. This vortex acts as a seal forcing OTL flow to contract over it. If the squealer cavity is wide enough, flow contracting over the PS corner vortex will impinge on the cavity floor. Also, because of the relative movement of the casing, part of the OTL flow will get trapped in the middle of the squealer cavity and form a scrapping vortex. In this case, additional suction side corner vortex can be formed in the corner between SS rim and the cavity floor as shown by Pátý et al. [11], Li et al. [12] and Du et al. [13].

Winglet tips mitigate the OTL flow by reducing the pressure difference that drives the leakage flow [14]. Similar as in the case of flat tips, OTL flow entering the tip gap of flat winglets creates a separation bubble at the PS edge, narrowing the effective tip gap. Because of overhangs, OTL flow has to travel further distance to leave the tip gap, causing lower mismatch angle with the main flow and mitigating the mixing losses [15]. Vincekovic et al. [16] did an aerodynamic winglet optimisation which was later used as a basis for the tip topology optimisation. They found that combining winglet with topology free squealer tip considerable efficiency benefit can be achieved. Coull et al. [17] did a survey of flat tip winglets looking at the aerodynamic efficiency and the heat load placing the overhangs at different locations around the tip perimeter. All the winglets tested brought considerable efficiency improvements injecting the OTL flow further from the blade into the region of higher pressure, decreasing mixing losses. Designs with full perimeter overhangs were found to be the most efficient, but with the highest heat load. It was found that early SS winglets decreased or only slightly increased the heat load but still keeping the efficiency improvement, compared to the flat tip.

Wheeler et al. [18] compared the low speed and high speed tip flow heat transfer. They found that tip heat transfer is largely dependent on the tip region Mach number with decrease of heat transfer as the Mach number increases. In high speed flows, the rear part of the tip was found to be subjected to decreased heat transfer level as the flow get supersonic contracting within a tip gap over the separation bubble and formed boundary layer. Viridi et al. [19] examined the effect of tip gap size on heat transfer for subsonic and transonic flows. It was found that in the case of subsonic flow, mostly in the front part of the tip, heat transfer decreases with decrease of the tip gap. However, this effect was found to be the opposite for transonic flows. To use this effect, Zhang and He [20] proposed a new concept of tip shaping that allows the decrease of heat transfer by locally accelerating the tip leakage flow to transonic or supersonic state. They proposed that in the front part of the blade, where flow is usually subsonic, the tip is shaped to form convergent-divergent ducting, resulting in accelerated supersonic flow which decreases tip heat transfer. De Maesschalck et al. [21] used this effect in an optimisation to create the contoured tip shapes. It was found that these tip shapes have a great potential of reducing

the heat transfer through flow acceleration. However, with the efficiency penalty.

With ever desired increase of the gas turbine efficiency, driven by higher turbine entry temperatures, turbine tips are getting more difficult to design and safely operate. So far, standard first step practice of designing a high pressure turbine components including aerodynamic and heat transfer was to obtain a blade heat flux or blade heat transfer coefficient for a single surface temperature, avoiding computationally expensive conjugate heat transfer computations [22]. Between the two, getting a HTC information is more valuable as it can be used to obtain heat flux information for different wall temperatures and as an input for finite element analysis. However, because of interactions between aerodynamics and non-adiabatic wall temperature, obtaining a HTC at a single wall temperature and scaling it across different wall temperatures can introduce large errors as shown by Maffulli and He [23]. They proposed a HTC local non-linear correction method which is used to correct the HTC for a range of temperatures that designer is interested in. Zhang and He [24] investigated the effect of wall temperature on heat transfer and OTL mass flow for the case of transonic turbine tip. They found that HTC distributions obtained at engine-representative and near-adiabatic wall temperatures by assuming linear heat transfer equation can differ for up to 30%. Different wall temperatures were also found to have a considerable effect on the OTL leakage flow. As a result, they have adopted the non-linear correction method from Maffulli and He [23] and demonstrated that with correcting the HTC information for a range of temperatures more reliable and consistent heat transfer prediction can be obtained.

In this work, aerodynamic and aerothermal winglet tip optimisations with and without constraints have been carried out. In the constrained optimisation, turbine inlet capacity and stage reaction were treated as constraints. This is important from turbine design point of view as the constrained capacity means unmodified mass flow through the turbine. Turbine reaction was constrained to ensure constant turbine stage expansion level and avoid change on disk loading. Constrained turbine capacity and reaction mean fair comparison between different tip designs and unaffected condition for design of upstream and downstream gas turbine components.

III. Problem Description

A. Geometry parametrization

This study was done on the MT1 turbine [25]. The MT1 turbine is a high pressure, full annulus research turbine consisting of 32 stator and 60 rotor blades. Its geometry is presented in Fig. 1. The rotor tip gap used was 1.5% of the blade span and constant for all presented cases.

Fig. 1 MT1 turbine geometry

The winglet tip geometry was parametrized and created using PADRAM, Rolls-Royce in-house tool for geometry parametrization and mesh generation [26]. The parametrization process is illustrated in Fig. 2. Starting from the datum tip outline (Fig. 2a), the winglet tip outline is controlled at 5 locations. LE, PS, and SS have one winglet control point each and there are two at the TE, one for PS and the SS. Locations of LE and TE control points are fixed. PS and SS

control points are allowed to move along the PS and SS, respectively. Once the PS and SS locations are determined, desired overhang value is specified as a percentage of datum tip axial chord on each control point. Five control points are then moved for in normal direction from the datum outline for specified overhang value and interpolated between along datum outline to form the winglet tip outline. Thickness of the winglet in spanwise direction is controlled as the straight length at each of 5 control points (Fig 2b). With straight length determined, winglet tip is extruded towards the hub in spanwise direction. After that, at each control point, blending angle under which extruded tip merges with the blade is determined. Finally, smoothing is applied between control points to ensure a continuous winglet shape. Overall, winglet tip was parametrized using 17 design parameters.

Alongside tip parametrization, this optimisation included blade skew for the rotor blade. This is illustrated in Fig 2c. From the datum (black), blade was skewed for positive (red) or negative (green) angle around the blade center. Skewing the rotor blade was done using a single parameter.

Fig. 2 Blade parametrization

IV. Methodology

A. Optimisation objectives

In aerodynamic optimisation, as optimisation objective, adiabatic efficiency was used. It was calculated using surface average of total enthalpy as given in Eq. 1.

$$\eta = \frac{h_{0,inlet} - h_{0,outlet}}{h_{0,inlet} - h_{0_{is},outlet}} \quad (1)$$

In the aerothermal optimisation, alongside adiabatic efficiency, surface integrated HTC was used to define the optimisation objective. HTC was obtained using non-linear heat transfer equation proposed by Maffulli and He [23] in Eq. 2. This way, HTC is composed of constant h_0 and a correction for certain wall temperature $h_1 T_w$ as given in Eq. 3. Compared to the conventional approach of using surface integral of heat flux or obtaining HTC in near-adiabatic condition and scaling it to a desired wall temperature, this approach enables more accurate heat load information without the need of doing expensive conjugate heat transfer simulations. Since HTC is obtained and corrected for a specific wall temperature, it gives more consistent and reliable comparison between different tip designs.

$$q = (h_0 + h_1 T_w)(T_w - T_{aw}) \quad (2)$$

$$HTC = h_0 + h_1 T_w \quad (3)$$

In Eq. 3, h_0 , h_1 and T_{aw} are three unknowns at each mesh point. To solve these, three separate numerical simulations with different rotor blade wall temperatures were done. To decide on values of rotor blade wall temperatures, temperature ratio (TR) value is introduced, as given in Eq. 4. TR is defined as the ratio of rotor blade surface temperature over the total temperature at the turbine stage inlet. Since the aim of this study was to model heat load for engine realistic condition, HTC was calculated for the rotor blade wall temperature corresponding to TR of 0.6. To successfully correct

the HTC around rotor blade temperature corresponding to TR of 0.6, alongside adiabatic simulation, two simulations were done by imposing constant rotor blade wall temperature corresponding to TR of 0.5 and 0.75. This has enabled to obtain HTC information in rotor blade wall temperature range from TR of 0.5 until adiabatic condition. Finally, with h_0 , h_1 and T_{aw} resolved, HTC was calculated using Eq. 3 and wall temperature corresponding to TR of 0.6.

$$TR = \frac{T_{rotor\ blade}}{T_{0,inlet}} \quad (4)$$

With both adiabatic efficiency and HTC obtained, aerothermal optimisation objective was calculated with combining efficiency and HTC objectives as

$$f(x) = \alpha f_1(x) + (1 - \alpha) f_2(x) \quad (5)$$

where α was the weighing factor. Separate objectives were calculated as given in Eq. 6 and 7 where x_{ref} represents the datum rotor blade tip shown in the Fig. 1. Since adding the winglet tip affects the flow and therefore the heat transfer in the blade region below the tip, but also changes the area of the blade surface, it was necessary to consider the heat load over the whole blade surface. Therefore, in Eq. 7, HTC_{blade} was obtained as a surface integral over the whole blade surface.

$$f_1(x) = \frac{1 - \eta(x)}{1 - \eta(x_{ref})} \quad (6)$$

$$f_2(x) = \frac{HTC_{blade}(x)}{HTC_{blade}(x_{ref})} \quad (7)$$

B. Optimisation constraints

Turbine inlet capacity (Φ) and turbine stage reaction (Λ) were set as constraints with allowed change up to $\pm 0.5\%$ from the datum value. They were calculated as presented in Eq. 8 and Eq. 9.

$$\Phi = \frac{\dot{m}_0 \sqrt{T_{0,inlet}}}{p_{0,inlet}} \quad (8)$$

$$\Lambda = \frac{T_{rotor\ inlet} - T_{rotor\ outlet}}{T_{stator\ inlet} - T_{rotor\ outlet}} \quad (9)$$

To allow for the correction of inlet capacity and stage reaction, blade skew was introduced as a parameter. Before deciding on blade skew value, study of turbine inlet capacity and stage reaction change with stator and rotor blade skew was done. Results are presented in the Fig. 3. Study was done by skewing the stator or the rotor blade only at the time, while keeping the other at the datum value. Blue lines present the change of inlet capacity and stage reaction while skewing the stator blade. It can be seen that by skewing the stator blade both inlet capacity and the stage reaction change with blade skew almost linearly, increasing both properties with positive stator blade skew. After applying either positive or negative stator blade skew for more than 0.1 degree, both values change for more than 0.5% from the datum value (dashed lines in Fig. 3). Regarding the rotor blade skew, it was found that it has less effect than the stator blade skew. While changing the stage reaction for the significant amount, rotor blade skew was found to have only minor effect on the inlet capacity by keeping the inlet capacity inside allowed change of 0.5% for blade skew values ranging from -1 to 1 degree. This was found to be because the MT-1 turbine is choked in the stator domain, therefore inlet capacity is limited by the throat area of the stator. After initial tests, it was found that addition of the winglet tip is unlikely to decrease the rotor throat area below the stator value and significantly change the inlet capacity. Therefore, to correct the inlet capacity and stage reaction in the optimisation, only rotor skew was used.

C. Optimiser

For this work, multi-point approximation method (MAM) optimiser was used [27, 28]. MAM is an iterative gradient based method that solves a sequence of constrained optimisation sub-problems by approximating the objective function and its constraints in a series of trust regions. Around the starting point, a generation of designs are chosen by the design of experiments (DOE) for which the simulations are carried out. A response surface is created for this generation and sub-optimal point is found. New trust region is created around sub-optimal point and new generation of designs

Fig. 3 Turbine inlet capacity and stage reaction change for stator and rotor skew

are tested. This process is iteratively repeated until convergence on the optimal design. MAM is available inside Rolls-Royce in-house optimisation tool, SOFT [29]. The optimisation workflow is illustrated in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Optimisation workflow

D. Numerical model

Steady RANS simulations were performed for single stage, one passage, consisting of stator and rotor blade. This was done using Hydra, Rolls-Royce in-house tool with $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model. Boundary conditions used are presented in Tab. 1. At stator inlet, uniform total pressure and temperature were imposed. Interface between stator and rotor domain was modelled using mixing plane, averaging the flow properties in circumferential direction. Static pressure distribution was used at the rotor outlet. All walls were modelled with no-slip condition and adiabatic in aerodynamic optimisation.

Fully structured multiblock O-H mesh was generated using PADRAM, presented in Fig. 5. Mesh sensitivity study was performed on arbitrary, full overhang winglet tip blade and is presented in Tab. 2. During this study, stator mesh was not modified in any way and was kept constant at size of around 2 million cells. Simulations were performed for whole stage, with three different rotor meshes. Three properties were monitored, efficiency increase compared to the datum blade, OTL mass flow normalized by 1 rotor passage mass flow and ratio of tip to blade heat transfer. As presented in Tab. 2, all tested meshes predicted efficiency increase with negligible variations. However, looking into OTL mass flow and heat flux two finer meshes showed slightly distinct results from the coarsest one. Therefore, it was decided to use 6 million mesh for the rotor domain in the optimisations. Overall, stage mesh had around 8 million cells

Table 1 Boundary conditions

Boundary	Condition
Stator inlet	p_0, T_0
Stator outlet	mixing plane
Rotor inlet	mixing plane
Rotor outlet	p_{st}
Endwalls, stator blade	No-slip adiabatic walls
Rotor blade	No-slip adiabatic walls or No-slip constant wall temperature

Table 2 Rotor mesh sensitivity study

Mesh size [million]	Efficiency increase [%]	OTL mass flow [%]	Tip to blade heat flux ratio [%]
3	0.28	3.87	21.13
6	0.31	4.14	20.73
12	0.32	4.14	20.88

and $y+$ values were at the order of 1.

Fig. 5 PADRAM mesh

E. Experimental validation

Numerical model was validated for the case of the flat tip datum blade against the experimental data from Simone et al. [30]. Isentropic Mach number was calculated at midspan for the stator blade and is presented in Fig. 6a. Numerical results show very good agreement against experimental data in all regions apart from aft SS side where numerical results predict a shock. This behaviour has been reported in previous steady state studies and shown that unsteady simulation averages out this phenomena [31].

Non-dimensional static pressure is presented at midspan for the rotor blade in Fig. 6b. It can be seen that numerical results slightly overpredict the static pressure at both PS and the SS side. Deviation against the experimental data is however lower at the PS. This has been investigated by few studies before using also unsteady higher fidelity simulations and no better fit was found [32].

(a) Stator blade isentropic Mach number at 50% span (b) Rotor blade non-dimensional static pressure at 50% span

Fig. 6 MT1 turbine experimental validation

To ensure the accuracy of CFD solution in the tip region, numerical model used in this work was validated against the experimental data from high speed linear cascade given by Zhang et al. [7]. For this case, experimental data is available in the form of tip Nusselt number contours for three tip gaps of 0.5%, 1% and 1.5% of the span. Nusselt number was calculated as given in Eq. 10 where C_{ax} stands for axial chord and k for thermal conductivity. Experimental data is given alongside numerical results in the Fig. 7. At the front part of the tip, experiments show increased level of Nusselt number. This is due to the fact that the flow is subsonic in this region which leads to increased level of heat transfer and heat transfer coefficient, hence increased Nusselt number. As the gap opens up, the size of this region increases, creating U-like shape. Present CFD results predict this shape and the increase of heat transfer and therefore the Nusselt number with opening of the tip gap well. However, the magnitude of the heat transfer is overpredicted by CFD results to some extent at 0.5% and 1% tip gaps. Aft region of the blade is characterised with the supersonic flow and therefore, decreased level of heat transfer which lead to decreased Nusselt number. Experimental data show lines of slightly increased heat transfer alongside the PS edge due to the reattachment of leakage flow, especially at the bigger tip gaps. That phenomena is generally over predicted by CFD results for all the tip gaps. This is explained by the unknown finite tip edge radius of manufactured cascade blades used in the experiment which were modelled as a sharp edge in the CFD cases. After the PS reattachment zone, CFD simulations of 1% and 1.5% tip gap show the stripes of decreased and increased Nusselt number due to the supersonic flow and shock reflections between the tip and the casing. This phenomena is visible in experimental data only in the case of 1.5% tip gap. Regardless of over prediction of heat transfer in some areas, overall present CFD results show reasonable agreement against experimental data capturing the correct flow patterns and changes of the flow and heat transfer magnitude with opening of the tip gap.

$$Nu = \frac{C_{ax} HTC}{k} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 7 High speed linear cascade Nusselt number validation: top, experiments [7]; bottom, present CFD computations

V. Results

A. Unconstrained aerodynamic optimisation

To set up a reference point for aerothermal optimisation, aerodynamic winglet optimisation was done first, without inlet capacity and stage reaction constraints. Also, it did not include any blade skew. Its objective was adiabatic efficiency and it took almost 200 iterations to converge. Optimisation history is presented in Fig. 8. It can be seen that almost all the designs tested had larger efficiency than the baseline datum tip. This is the characteristic of winglet tips where larger overhangs usually mean larger efficiency. However, some designs achieved lower efficiency despite the large, full perimeter overhangs. And the most efficient winglet is usually not the one with the largest allowed overhangs. Therefore, the most efficient design is presented next to identify the winglet characteristics that increase the aerodynamic performance.

Fig. 8 Aerodynamic winglet optimisation history

The most efficient tip design is presented in Fig. 9. Optimised winglet outline is presented alongside datum tip outline (red) alongside three cross sections. Optimised novel winglet tip features full perimeter overhang apart from the TE SS. Interestingly, at mid-PS, overhang is rather small, as shown in cross section B-B. At all other overhang control points, overhang is maximum allowed. As shown in the cross sections, winglet tip features sharp edges at all control points, with effectively zero straight length, which are prone to increased heating, showing the importance of aero-thermal assessment. Optimised tip properties are given in Tab. 3. Alongside considerable efficiency increase, optimised winglet tip significantly increased the turbine stage reaction when compared to the datum tip, showing the importance of constrained optimisation. Turbine inlet capacity of optimised tip has decreased by -0.13% which is well inside the allowed limits.

Fig. 9 Optimised winglet tip

Since OTL flow is driven by the pressure difference around the tip, static pressure is plotted around the optimum winglet tip and compared to the datum blade. This is shown in the Fig. 10 where static pressure is plotted against axial chord. 0 value of axial chord corresponds to the LE and 1 to the TE. Starting from the LE, it can be seen that the

Table 3 Aerodynamic optimisation results

Property	Change from the datum [%]
Adiabatic efficiency	+1.13
Inlet capacity	-0.13
Stage reaction	+1.72

whole region around the LE is in the region of higher pressure in the case of winglet tip. In the case of datum tip SS static pressure starts rapidly decreasing around the 0.1 of the axial chord where in the case of the winglet tip SS static pressure decrease is much smaller. This is caused by the absence of SS corner vortex in the case of winglet tip that does not decrease the SS static pressure. This vortex originates from the LE SS in the case of the datum tip and combined with early formation of OTL vortex on the blade SS, leads to much greater pressure difference in the case of the datum tip for the first half of the tip. Only after around 0.8 of the axial chord pressure differences between the two are comparable where at that point winglet SS static pressure stops decreasing and remains roughly constant until the TE. The reason for this was found to be the absence of the TE SS overhang that causes the low pressure core OTL vortex to detach from the blade tip, entraining less of the OTL flow.

Fig. 10 Static pressure distribution around datum and optimised winglet tip

B. Inlet capacity and stage reaction correction of unconstrained optimum winglet tip

Optimum design presented in Fig. 9 was additionally corrected to match the inlet capacity and stage reaction with allowed deviation from the datum value. As presented in Tab. 3, only stage reaction deviates from the datum value for more than $\pm 0.5\%$. To decide on the required skew needed to bring the stage reaction in the desired window, turbine inlet capacity and stage reaction change for stator and rotor skew was investigated as shown in the Fig. 11. Starting from the unconstrained aerodynamic optimum with no stator or rotor blade skew, turbine inlet capacity and stage reaction are plotted for the stator and rotor blade skew ranging from -1 to 1 degree. Following the trendline of stage reaction it can be seen that either stator skew of around -0.3 degree or rotor skew of around -0.5 degree (red dot in Fig. 11b) brings the stage reaction to the desired value. However, as shown before, stator blade skew has big effect on the inlet capacity

Table 4 Additionally corrected optimum design results

Property	Change from the datum [%]
Adiabatic efficiency	+1.04
Inlet capacity	+0.10
Stage reaction	-0.09

where rotor blade skew of -0.5 degree (red dot in Fig. 11a) still keeps the capacity inside allowed deviation from the datum case. Therefore, to bring both inlet capacity and stage reaction into the acceptable change window, rotor blade skew of -0.5 degrees was used.

Fig. 11 Turbine inlet capacity and stage reaction change for stator and rotor skew of aerodynamically optimised winglet tip

Results of optimised winglet tip correction are presented in the Tab. 4. It can be seen that decreasing the reaction to acceptable value has slightly decreased the efficiency of optimised winglet tip.

C. Inlet capacity and stage reaction constrained aerodynamic optimisation

Constrained aerodynamic optimisation was performed with winglet parametrization as in the unconstrained aerodynamic optimisation presented in section A with addition of rotor blade skew to account for turbine inlet capacity and stage reaction changes. Most published optimisation work does not include these constraints leading to in-practical designs. This optimisation took around 210 iterations to converge and its results are presented in the Fig. 12. Turbine inlet capacity for all designs tested is shown in Fig. 12a. It can be seen that in the early stage of optimisation there is a higher variation of inlet capacity due to the larger rotor blade skew applied. Also, some designs with rather small blending angles (Fig. 2) were tried, creating thick winglets that significantly reduced the rotor domain throat area that further changed the capacity. As those designs are not just infeasible but also inefficient, they were quickly discarded and the inlet capacity was successfully constrained.

Stage reaction change is presented in the Fig. 12b. It was found that the stage reaction is much more sensitive to the rotor blade skew compared to the inlet capacity and it took longer for it to converge. After around 120 iterations stage reaction was constrained to allowed values but was always kept close to the upper limit. The reason for this is the fact that greater the stage reaction, larger the efficiency. Therefore the optimiser kept the stage reaction on the upper limit to use all of it potential for efficiency increase.

Efficiency is presented for all the designs tested in the Fig. 12c and for successfully constrained designs in the Fig. 12d where both figures are normalised against the lowest achieved efficiency. From around 210 iterations done, 82 were successfully constrained, mostly in the later stage of the optimisation. The optimisation converged towards

Table 5 Constrained optimum tip design results

Property	Change from the datum [%]
Adiabatic efficiency	+1.07
Inlet capacity	+0.04
Stage reaction	+0.43

the optimum winglet design presented in the unconstrained aerodynamic optimisation (section A) with some minor differences at the PS overhang. Its properties are presented in Tab. 5. As shown in the Tab. 5 property changes of this design are similar to the optimum unconstrained and additionally corrected design explained in the section B.

Fig. 12 Constrained aerodynamic optimisation history

To examine the differences between novel unconstrained and additionally corrected and constrained optimum designs,

tip designs with static pressure around the tips are presented in the Fig. 13. As explained in the section B, unconstrained - additionally corrected tip was corrected with rotor skew of -0.5 degrees. Rotor skew used in the constrained optimisation for the optimum design was -0.17 degrees. Difference between applied blade skews can be seen in the Fig. 13a as the additionally corrected tip is rotated more in the clockwise direction around the blade center. Interestingly, PS overhangs are differently placed between the two tips where constrained optimum has larger PS overhang placed closer to the TE. This is not the case for the additionally corrected tip where the larger PS overhang is placed closer to the LE. This has slightly changed the static pressure distribution around the tip, mostly at the PS, as presented in the Fig. 13b. However, these differences are small having minor effect on the flow between the two tips.

Fig. 13 Comparison of optimum unconstrained - additionally corrected and constrained winglet tips

D. Inlet capacity and stage reaction aerothermal optimisation

Aerothermal optimisation for adiabatic efficiency and HTC was done by combining efficiency and HTC objectives. Optimisation with equal weighing of the objectives in Eq. 5 ($\alpha = 0.5$) was done first. Its results are presented as the Pareto front in the Fig. 14. Results are plotted as efficiency change against HTC change from the datum blade. As presented, all designs tested had increased value of integrated HTC, compared to the datum, as addition of the winglet will increase the blade area therefore increase the integrated HTC. However, some winglets behave better heat load-wise than others where for similar efficiency benefit HTC increase is much smaller. Since increased HTC means more heat load on the blade, it requires more cooling. Therefore, HTC wants to be minimised for a certain efficiency benefit. Trade-off between the two is presented as Pareto front in the Fig. 14. Designs in red are the ones that did not satisfy the constraints and the ones in blue are successfully constrained. Most of the successfully constrained designs are located on the Pareto front as these were created at the later stage in the optimisation. Population of the Pareto front with both unconstrained and constrained designs proves that Pareto front is resolved and that the optimisation has converged.

Fig. 14 Pareto front for aerothermal optimisation with equal objectives weights

To populate the other areas of Pareto front, two other optimisations with different objective weights were done and alongside equal weight optimisation, are presented in the Fig. 15. HTC dominated optimisation, presented in green in Fig. 15, put more emphasis on reducing the integrated HTC by using weight of $\alpha = 0.25$. It can be seen that in this optimisation, some designs that have significant efficiency improvements for only minor increase in HTC have been identified. Other optimisation done was the efficiency dominated one where weight of $\alpha = 0.75$ was used. That explored the Pareto front area around constrained aerodynamic optimum tip presented in the section C. As the objective definition had single minimum objective solution, optimiser has clustered points around that point in search for a minimum, leaving other regions of Pareto slightly unpopulated. To resolve that, other weights could be used. However, trend of Pareto front as HTC augmentation with efficiency increase is visible.

Fig. 15 Pareto front for aerothermal optimisations with different objective weights

From Pareto front showed in the Fig. 15, three novel winglet tips have been selected for further investigation. Winglet 1, with the lowest HTC increase for efficiency improvement of 1%, winglet 2 as the most efficient design with HTC increase below 1% and winglet 3 as the most efficient design with the lowest HTC.

Fig. 16 presents slices of relative total pressure for 3 selected winglets. Winglet 1 features overhangs at all regions of the tip apart from the TE SS, similar as the aerodynamic optimum presented in section C. Large overhangs on the PS

and PS TE reduce the amount of leakage flow and inject it into the area of higher pressure, reducing the mixing losses due to shearing. Also, OTL vortex detached from the blade is beneficial in terms of heat load as rubbing the OTL vortex on the blade increases the heat transfer. Winglets 2 and 3 have higher amount of OTL flow visible as the larger OTL vortex area, compared to the winglet 1. Both winglet 2 and 3 have only small PS TE overhangs which were found to be beneficial for injecting the OTL vortex into the region of higher pressure, detaching it from the blade SS.

Fig. 16 Slices of relative total pressure

HTC contours on winglet tips are presented in Fig. 17. As the flow enters the tip gap, it is contracted over the tip edge forming a circulation bubble along the PS rim. Flow contracting over the circulation bubble then impinges on the blade tip creating a hotspots of increased heat transfer visible as stripes of high HTC alongside LE and second half of the PS. Behind those stripes, towards the SS, HTC level is higher at the front part of the tip, compared to the second half of the tip. The reason for this is subsonic flow in the first half of the tip and as the flow gets supersonic in the second half, the rate of heat transfer drops. Stripes of low and high HTC can be seen closer to the TE on winglet tip 1 and near the SS in the second half of tips 2 and 3. This is due to the shock reflections between the tip and the casing, where shock impingements cause stripes of increased HTC. All overhangs increase the HTC level not only as they add on the area, but also because they usually guide vortices that rub on them, increasing the HTC level. This is particularly the case for early SS overhang where its underside experiences larger HTC as the PV originates. Underside of large PS TE overhang of winglet 1 was found to be the area of highest HTC.

Fig. 17 HTC distribution on winglet tips

Figure 18 presents the variation of efficiency and HTC with the tip gap size. Apart from the tip gap of 1.5% of the span used in the optimisations, two other gaps of 0.5 and 2.5% of the span have been tested. As expected, efficiency fall almost linearly for all the winglets presented. However, winglet tips retain their efficiency benefits compared to the datum at larger tip gap, but this advantage significantly reduces at the smaller tip gap. At tip gap of 0.5% of the span, winglets 2 and 3 has similar efficiency to the datum blade and winglet 1, which has 1% higher efficiency at baseline tip gap, is only 0.3% more efficient than the datum.

HTC of winglet 1 increases with the opening of the tip gap which is in line with the findings from Zhang et al. [7]. However, this is not the case for winglet 2 and 3 and the datum tip with opening the tip gap from 1.5 to 2.5% of the blade span where HTC stays roughly constant. Similar behaviour for low heat load winglets was found in the study by Coull et al. [17].

Fig. 18 Variation of efficiency and HTC with tip gap size

VI. Conclusions

This paper deals with multidisciplinary optimisation of high pressure turbine rotor winglet tips. Methodology that includes aerothermal objective combining adiabatic efficiency with locally corrected surface integrated HTC has been presented. Optimisation included constraints in terms of turbine inlet capacity and stage reaction which were allowed to change up to $\pm 0.5\%$ from the datum value. To authors knowledge these constraints are often missing in other published literature but are crucially important for a practical design. It was found that addition of winglet tips has small effect on the inlet capacity and significant impact on the stage reaction. Methodology for correction of unconstrained tip designs has also been presented.

Winglet tips were confirmed to increase the efficiency by decreasing the amount of leakage flow as a result of decrease of the pressure difference across the tip gap that drives the leakage flow. Aerodynamic optimum winglet from the work has led to increase the stage efficiency by 1.07% subject to the inlet capacity and stage reaction constraints.

Pareto front in two objective aerothermal optimisation was generated by performing three different optimisation runs with different objective weights. It was found that this approach can be used to identify the Pareto region and further refine it using different objective weights, providing design engineers for the choice of balanced efficiency and heating solutions for practical problems.

Three novel winglet tips from the Pareto front have been analysed. It was found that SS overhangs bring efficiency improvement with little increase of the heat load. PS and LE overhangs were found to further increase the efficiency but with some considerable heat load. Underside of the PS was found to be particularly prone to the aerodynamic heating.

Winglets were also tested for different tip gaps. It was found that low heat load winglets lose their performance benefits as the tip gap reduces. At larger tip gap winglets performed similarly as at the baseline tip gap, compared to the datum. Opening of the tip gap was found to mostly increase the blade heat transfer level. However, low heat load winglets and the datum tip were found to have almost constant heat load as the gap increased from the baseline tip gap.

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References

- [1] Denton, J. D., “Loss Mechanisms in Turbomachines,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 115, No. 4, 1993, pp. 621–656.
- [2] Harvey, N., “Turbine Blade Tip Design and Tip Clearance Treatment, VKI Lecture Series,” 2004.
- [3] Bunker, R. S., “Axial turbine blade tips: function, design, and durability,” *Journal of propulsion and power*, Vol. 22, No. 2, 2006, pp. 271–285.
- [4] Bunker, R. S., “Blade Tip Heat Transfer and Cooling Desing Introduction: Motivation and Turbine Requirements, VKI Lecture Series,” 2006.
- [5] Coull, J. D., and Atkins, N. R., “The influence of boundary conditions on tip leakage flow,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 137, No. 6, 2015.
- [6] Zhang, Q., O’Dowd, D., He, L., Wheeler, A., Ligrani, P., and Cheong, B., “Overtip shock wave structure and its impact on turbine blade tip heat transfer,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 133, No. 4, 2011.
- [7] Zhang, Q., O’Dowd, D., He, L., Oldfield, M., and Ligrani, P., “Transonic Turbine Blade Tip Aerothermal Performance With Different Tip Gaps—Part I: Tip Heat Transfer,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 133, No. 4, 2011.
- [8] Key, N. L., and Arts, T., “Comparison of Turbine Tip Leakage Flow for Flat Tip and Squealer Tip Geometries at High-Speed Conditions,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 128, No. 2, 2004, pp. 213–220.
- [9] Vass, P., and Arts, T., “Numerical investigation of high-pressure turbine blade tip flows: analysis of aerodynamics,” *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part A: Journal of Power and Energy*, Vol. 225, No. 7, 2011, pp. 940–953.
- [10] Yang, D., Yu, X., and Feng, Z., “Investigation of leakage flow and heat transfer in a gas turbine blade tip with emphasis on the effect of rotation,” *Journal of turbomachinery*, Vol. 132, No. 4, 2010.
- [11] Pátý, M., Cernat, B. C., De Maesschalck, C., and Lavagnoli, S., “Experimental and Numerical Investigation of Optimized Blade Tip Shapes—Part II: Tip Flow Analysis and Loss Mechanisms,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 141, No. 1, 2019.
- [12] Li, J., Du, K., and Song, L., “Effects of tip cavity geometries on the aerothermal performance of the transonic turbine blade with cavity tip,” *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part A: Journal of Power and Energy*, Vol. 230, No. 3, 2016, pp. 319–331.
- [13] Du, K., Li, Z., Li, J., and Sunden, B., “Influences of a multi-cavity tip on the blade tip and the over tip casing aerothermal performance in a high pressure turbine cascade,” *Applied Thermal Engineering*, Vol. 147, 2019, pp. 347–360.
- [14] Schabowski, Z., and Hodson, H., “The reduction of over tip leakage loss in unshrouded axial turbines using winglets and squealers,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 136, No. 4, 2014.
- [15] Coull, J. D., Atkins, N. R., and Hodson, H. P., “High efficiency cavity winglets for high pressure turbines,” *Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, Vol. 45622, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2014, p. V02CT38A005.
- [16] Vincekovic, L., John, A., Qin, N., and Shahpar, S., “Exploring Topology Optimisation of High Pressure Turbine Blade Tips,” *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2020: Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition. GT2020-16059*, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2020.
- [17] Coull, J. D., Atkins, N. R., and Hodson, H. P., “Winglets for improved aerothermal performance of high pressure turbines,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 136, No. 9, 2014.
- [18] Wheeler, A. P., Atkins, N. R., and He, L., “Turbine blade tip heat transfer in low speed and high speed flows,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 133, No. 4, 2011.
- [19] Viridi, A., Zhang, Q., He, L., Li, H., and Hunsley, R., “Aerothermal performance of shroudless turbine blade tips with relative casing movement effects,” *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, Vol. 31, No. 2, 2015, pp. 527–536.
- [20] Zhang, Q., and He, L., “Tip-shaping for HP turbine blade aerothermal performance management,” *Journal of turbomachinery*, Vol. 135, No. 5, 2013.
- [21] De Maesschalck, C., Lavagnoli, S., Paniagua, G., Verstraete, T., Olive, R., and Picot, P., “Heterogeneous optimization strategies for carved and squealer-like turbine blade tips,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 138, No. 12, 2016.

- [22] Starke, C., Janke, E., Hofer, T. s., and Lengani, D., “Comparison of a conventional thermal analysis of a turbine cascade to a full conjugate heat transfer computation,” *Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, Vol. 43147, 2008, pp. 1013–1024.
- [23] Maffulli, R., and He, L., “Impact of wall temperature on heat transfer coefficient and aerodynamics for three-dimensional turbine blade passage,” *Journal of Thermal Science and Engineering Applications*, Vol. 9, No. 4, 2017.
- [24] Zhang, Q., and He, L., “Impact of wall temperature on turbine blade tip aerothermal performance,” *Journal of engineering for gas turbines and power*, Vol. 136, No. 5, 2014.
- [25] Beard, P. F., Povey, T., and Chana, K. S., “Turbine efficiency measurement system for the QinetiQ Turbine Test Facility,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 132, No. 1, 2010.
- [26] *PADRAM: Parametric Design and Rapid Meshing System for Complex Turbomachinery Configurations*, Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air, Vol. Volume 8: Turbomachinery, Parts A, B, and C, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2012-69030>, URL <https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2012-69030>.
- [27] Polynkin, A., Toropov, V., and Shahpar, S., “Adaptive and parallel capabilities in the Multipoint Approximation Method,” *AIAA/ISSMO Multidisciplinary Analysis and Optimization Conference*, AIAA, 2008. URL <http://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/4766/>.
- [28] Caloni, S., Shahpar, S., and Toropov, V., “Multi-Disciplinary Design Optimisation of the Cooled Squealer Tip for High Pressure Turbines,” *Aerospace*, Vol. 5, No. 4, 2018, p. 116.
- [29] Shahpar, S., “SOFT : A New Design and Optimisation Tool for Turbomachinery,” *Evolutionary Methods for Design, Optimisation and Control*, 2002. URL <https://ci.nii.ac.jp/naid/10012934785/en/>.
- [30] Simone, S., Montomoli, F., Martelli, F., Chana, K. S., Qureshi, I., and Povey, T., “Analysis on the effect of a nonuniform inlet profile on heat transfer and fluid flow in turbine stages,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 134, No. 1, 2012.
- [31] Beard, P., Smith, A., and Povey, T., “Experimental and computational fluid dynamics investigation of the efficiency of an unshrouded transonic high pressure turbine,” *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part A: Journal of Power and Energy*, Vol. 225, No. 8, 2011, pp. 1166–1179.
- [32] Salvadori, S., Montomoli, F., Martelli, F., Adami, P., Chana, K., and Castillon, L., “Aerothermal study of the unsteady flow field in a transonic gas turbine with inlet temperature distortions,” *Journal of Turbomachinery*, Vol. 133, No. 3, 2011.